

Nutrients and Hypertension: A Cross-sectional Study of Dietary Pattern in Northern India

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hypertension is a major public health concern, contributing significantly to cardiovascular disease, stroke and related complications. However, rural populations often lack access to nutritional education, leading to poor dietary practices that exacerbate hypertension.

Objectives: To evaluate and compare the dietary patterns-including the type and frequency of food item consumption and lifestyle-related risk factors among hypertensive and normotensive individuals in Northern India.

Methodology: A community-based, cross-sectional study enrolled adult women aged 18-69 years residing in Punjab, India, with a total sample of 2,160 participants selected using a multistage sampling design. Baseline interviews were conducted over a 16-month period, from January 2022 to April 2023. The study followed the WHO STEPwise approach for Non-communicable disease surveillance (STEPS) to estimate the prevalence and risk factors of hypertension across three age groups (18-29, 30-44, and 45-69 years).

Results: A total of 2160 females were screened for hypertension. 827 (38.27%) were found to be hypertensive, with 27.9% in stage 1 and 10.4% in stage 2 HTN. Significant dietary differences were observed between hypertensive and normotensive individuals. Hypertensives consumed more cereals ($P=0.005$), fewer legumes ($P=0.001$) and leafy vegetables ($P=0.001$), but more non-leafy vegetables ($P=0.001$). Additional significant associations included higher intake of fast food, junk food, dry fruits, fresh juice and caffeine-rich drinks (all $P \leq 0.001$), along with lower water consumption ($P=0.001$). Hypertensive individuals were also more likely to use unhealthy fats ($P=0.003$), change cooking oil less frequently ($P=0.020$), and consume higher levels of sugar ($P=0.003$), salt ($P=0.001$), table salt ($P=0.041$) and pickles ($P=0.001$).

Conclusion: Unhealthy dietary habits- particularly excessive intake of salt, sugar and processed foods are significantly associated with hypertension in rural populations. These findings highlight the need for targeted dietary education and lifestyle interventions to reduce hypertension risk and promote cardiovascular health.

Keywords: Dietary practices, High blood pressure, Lifestyle, Rural, Diseases

I. Introduction

Hypertension is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases and a leading contributor to global mortality. Data published by the Global Health Advocacy Incubator (GHA) indicates that Punjab has a hypertension prevalence rate of 35.7%, significantly higher than the national average of 25.3%, making it an ideal setting for testing last-mile healthcare innovations [1]-[2].

In recent years, the association between diet, nutrition, and hypertension has garnered considerable attention [3]-[4]. Compared to complex dietary patterns, analyzing dietary intake at the food group level offers greater interpretability and facilitates the translation of findings into practical dietary recommendations for hypertension prevention [5]. Although many studies have explored the link between individual nutrients or specific foods and the development of hypertension among Chinese individuals, limited research has examined the effect of continuous intake patterns across various food groups within a single study [6]-[8]. Several studies have highlighted the critical role that dietary factors play in both the development and management of hypertension. Diets rich in sodium, added sugars, unhealthy fats and processed foods have been consistently associated with elevated blood pressure levels. For instance, high sodium intake is known to promote fluid retention, which can increase blood volume and subsequently, blood pressure. Conversely, diets abundant in fruits, vegetables, whole grains and low-fat dairy products have been linked to lower blood pressure and improved cardiovascular health [9]-[10].

Understanding the intricate relationship between dietary factors and hypertension is vital for developing effective public health strategies. Targeted interventions aimed at promoting healthier eating habits can lead to significant reductions in hypertension prevalence and its associated complications. By focusing on education, accessibility and community engagement, healthcare providers can empower individuals to make informed dietary choices, ultimately improving health outcomes and reducing the burden of hypertension within vulnerable populations. This research underscores the need for a comprehensive approach to hypertension management, integrating dietary modifications alongside medical interventions.

II. Materials and methods

A. Study Design and Sampling

The study for screening of widespread hypertension in Punjab was carried in a systematic manner in accordance with the WHO stepwise approach for surveillance of hypertension with few modifications [11]. A proportionate allocation based on census distribution (2011) was used for rural areas [12]. A multistage, geographically clustered, probability-based sampling method was adopted. This involved a two-stage process, where villages served as the primary sampling units (PSUs). Within each selected PSU, households were chosen and the final sampling units consisted of individuals aged 18 to 69 years living in those households.

B. Sample Size

A total of 2,160 adult females were selected for the study using a multistage sampling design. Sample size estimates were derived using population data for each age group based on the 2011 Census. The sample size was collected by formula:-

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P (1-P)}{e^2}$$

Where,

Z=level of confidence (1.96)

P=baseline level of the indicators (0.5)

e=margin of error (0.05)

n= sample size

$$n=1.96^2*0.5(1-0.5)/0.05^2$$

$$n=384$$

However, sample 384 must be adjusted to account for the sample design's effect, the amount of age-sex estimates to be given and the expected non-response rate. To account for the design effect of the sample, multiply the sample size by the design effect. Since multistage sampling was employed, a design effect of 1.5 was applied for the survey, following the recommended guidelines. Moreover, the survey findings should be reported separately for each age group and gender. To get precise age-sex estimates, multiply the sample size by the number of age-sex groups. The number of age-sex estimates in a survey depends on the desired age range. In this study, which focused on women aged 18 to 69 years, three age groups were defined for analysis: 18-29, 30-44 and 45-69 years.

Adjusting for design effect and number of age-sex estimates =384*1.5*3

$$=1728$$

To adjust for anticipated non-response, divide sample (1728) by the anticipated response rate. A response rate of 80% is the recommended rate to anticipate.

Adjusting for anticipated non-response =1728/0.80

n=2160

After adjusting for the design effect and anticipating an 80% response rate, the total minimum estimated sample size of 2,160 was calculated by combining all age and gender groups. The cross-sectional survey was conducted in rural areas of Punjab according to 2011 census, estimated total population was 277.04 lakh i.e.173.4 lakh rural population (62.51%). [62.51-rural population, 37.49-urban population]. As per the 2011 Census, Punjab was segmented into 20 districts, with an estimated population was 277.04 lakh or 2.77 crores.

C. Data Collection

A structured, face-to-face interview was conducted at the residence of each eligible family member. The duration of each interview ranged from 30 to 45 minutes. Participant's age was verified by checking their ID proof during the interview. The baseline interview with subjects were conducted between January 2022 to April 2023. A preliminary pilot study was conducted to assess the feasibility of the main interventional study using a small sample size. Accordingly, a pilot study involving 100 participants was carried out in rural areas of Sangrur district, Punjab. Based on feedback, changes were made to the questionnaire content and the data collection procedure to ensure that the items accurately captured the intended variables and research objectives. The data collection process was divided into two phases: Phase I gathered demographic, socioeconomic status, disease-related information and dietary habits while Phase II involved physical assessments such as height, weight, blood pressure levels, waist circumference and hip circumference using standardized instruments and protocols.

D. Study Tool

A pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire was utilized to gather data, encompassing 11 sections that included both quantitative and qualitative information. The tool was initially developed in English and then translated into Punjabi and Hindi, ensuring consistency across all versions. The questionnaire was organized into multiple sections, each focusing on different aspects of the study such as, demographic information of household members, socio-economic status (SES) of Subjects, reproductive health status, Minichal scale for quality of life, history of illness in the last 12 months, history of disease in family, symptoms of hypertension, lifestyle related risk factors of hypertension, dietary pattern, anthropometric measurements and information on Covid-19.

E. Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University, Fatehgarh Sahib (SGGSWU/IEC/2023/14, Dated 13-10-2023). Written informed consent was secured from every participant prior to their involvement in the survey. This was done in accordance with established ethical guidelines. Subjects were assured of confidentiality and given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time.

F. Definitions

Uday Pareekh developed a scale to calculate and examine the socio-economic status (SES) of rural populations [13]. Additionally, information was documented in questionnaire regarding the items used, including average intake of salt, sugar, table salt and pickles, as well as various cooking oils, such as desi ghee, vanaspati ghee, rice bran oil, refined oil, mustard oil, olive oil and any others. The WHO recommends that adults should consume 25-30 grams of cooking oil per day [14]. Oils high in saturated fat are linked to an increased risk of cardiovascular disease. Additionally, WHO advises keeping daily salt intake below 5 grams and suggests that free sugars should make up less than 10% of total daily energy intake [15]-[16]. The subjects were asked to estimate the frequency of consumption of each food groups in a week and their servings in a day were also recorded in the questionnaire. Body weight and height were used to calculate BMI, with the formula involving weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared (kg/m^2). The Asian-Pacific cut-off criteria include being underweight ($<18.5 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$), normal weight ($18.5\text{-}22.9 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$), overweight ($23\text{-}24.9 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$), or obese ($\geq 25 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$) with uncrossed legs before measurement [17]. As per ICMR (2010) guidelines, adult males with a waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) of 0.90 or higher and females with a WHR of 0.80 or above were considered obese [18]. For all 2,160 participants, both hypertensives and non-hypertensives, WHR was computed by dividing waist circumference by hip circumference, both measured in centimeters, and the results were compared against these criteria. Additionally, hypertension was identified either through the use of prescribed antihypertensive medication, regardless of the participant's current blood pressure, or if their systolic and/or diastolic pressure was $\geq 140/90 \text{ mmHg}$, based on the JNC VIII guidelines (Bell et al., 2015) [19].

G. Statistical analysis

The survey results were input into a database created specifically for the study using the SPSS 26.0 programme. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were produced for continuous variables, whereas frequencies and percentages were used to summarise qualitative data. Other statistical tests such as the Chi-square test and Mann-Whitney U test were used. A significance level of 0.05 was applied.

III. Results

In the present study, 2160 adult females were assessed for hypertension. Among them, 827 participants (38.30%) were identified as hypertensive. Of these, 602 women (27.9%) were classified as having stage 1 hypertension, while 225 women (10.4%) were found to have stage 2 hypertension (Figure 1).

Fig. 1 Prevalence and Stages of Hypertension among Adult Females

The analysis reveals significant disparities in hypertension (HTN) prevalence across various socio-demographic indicators. Caste shows marked differences, with the Agricultural Caste exhibiting the highest HTN rate (65.2%), followed by Lower Caste (25.3%) and Scheduled Caste (9.6%). Housing type is a key factor; individuals residing in huts report a notably lower HTN prevalence (0.8%) compared to those in pucca houses (31.1%). Educational level also correlates with HTN risk: illiterate individuals show the highest prevalence (64.6%) compared to graduates (1.7%). Occupational patterns reveal elevated HTN rates among laborers (71.0%) and cultivators (19.5%) compared to professionals and service workers. Socioeconomic status exhibited a significant association with HTN. Only 4.8% of hypertensive individuals were classified as upper middle class, compared to 14.3% of non-hypertensive individuals. In contrast, 45.9% of hypertensive individuals fell under the lower class category, while only 21.9% of non-hypertensives belonged to this group. Both differences were statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 157.398$, $P = 0.001$) (Table 1).

Table I

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF NORMOTENSIVE VERSUS HYPERTENSIVE SUBJECTS

		HYPERTENSION				Total	Chi-square value	P-value
		Normotensives		Hypertensives				
		No. of cases (n=1333)	% age	No. of cases (n=827)	% age			
Category	Scheduled Caste	188	14.1	79	9.6	267	19.047	0.001
	Lower Caste	396	29.7	209	25.3	605		
	Agriculture Caste	749	56.2	539	65.2	1288		
No. of Family Members	>5	384	28.8	202	24.4	586	4.956	0.028
	Up to 5	949	71.2	625	75.6	1574		
Land	No Land	608	45.6	581	70.3	1189	133.357	0.001
	<1 Acre land	282	21.2	111	13.4	393		
	1-5 Acre land	109	8.2	37	4.5	146		
	5-10 Acre land	101	7.6	26	3.1	127		
	10-15 Acre land	117	8.8	38	4.6	155		
	15-20 Acre land	85	6.4	32	3.9	117		
	≥20 Acre land	31	2.3	2	0.2	33		
House	Hut	58	4.4	7	0.8	65	23.363	0.001
	Kutch House	533	40.0	320	38.7	853		
	Mixed House	296	22.2	197	23.8	493		
	Pucca House	384	28.8	257	31.1	641		
	Mansion	62	4.7	46	5.6	108		
Farm power	No Draught Animals	892	66.9	546	66.0	1438	33.932	0.001
	1-2 Draught Animals	137	10.3	130	15.7	267		
	3-4 Draught Animals	179	13.4	119	14.4	298		
	5-6 Draught Animals	125	9.4	32	3.9	157		
Social Participation	None	1207	90.5	700	84.6	1907	17.205	0.001
	Member of 1 organization	126	9.5	127	15.4	253		
Material Possessions	Cycle	56	4.2	13	1.6	69	241.483	0.001
	Radio	215	16.1	260	31.4	475		
	Chairs	372	27.9	194	23.5	566		
	Mobile phone	165	12.4	127	15.4	292		
	Television	65	4.9	133	16.1	198		
	Refrigerators	460	34.5	100	12.1	560		
Education	Illiterate	516	38.7	534	64.6	1050	318.369	0.001
	Can Read Only	33	2.5	75	9.1	108		
	Can Read and Write	35	2.6	38	4.6	73		
	Primary	79	5.9	60	7.3	139		
	Middle	44	3.3	24	2.9	68		
	High School	379	28.4	75	9.1	454		
	Graduate	175	13.1	14	1.7	189		
And Above	72	5.4	7	0.8	79			
Occupation	None	3	0.2	0	0.0	3	240.754	0.001
	Labourer	502	37.7	587	71.0	1089		

	Business	76	5.7	10	1.2	86		
	Independent Profession	180	13.5	64	7.7	244		
	Cultivation	507	38.0	161	19.5	668		
	Service	65	4.9	5	0.6	70		
Socio-economic status (SES)	Upper Middle Class	190	14.3	40	4.8	230	157.398	0.001
	Middle Class	338	25.4	176	21.3	514		
	Lower Middle Class	513	38.5	231	27.9	744		
	Lower Class	292	21.9	380	45.9	672		

The analysis identified several significant factors associated with hypertension. Individuals with hypertension were more likely to use polluting cooking fuels like kerosene and biogas, and less likely to engage in vigorous physical activity. Although they reported frequent physical activity, it was mainly low-intensity household work. Poor sleep, especially sleeping five hours or less, and high or very low mobile phone use were also linked to hypertension. Additionally, emotional and physical stress were significantly higher among hypertensive individuals, while financial stress showed no association. These findings suggest that hypertension is strongly influenced by modifiable lifestyle and environmental factors (Table 2).

TABLE II

COMPARATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF LIFESTYLE VARIABLES AMONG NORMOTENSIVE AND HYPERTENSIVE WOMEN

		HYPERTENSION				Total	Chi-square value	P-value
		Normotensives		Hypertensives				
		No. of cases (n=1333)	% age	No. of cases (n= 827)	% age			
Alcohol consumption	No	1333	100	827	100	2160		
Smoking	No	1333	100	827	100	2160		
Type of fuel used for cooking	Electricity	1	0.1	0	0	1	18.195	0.006
	LPG	1251	93.8	743	89.8	1994		
	Biogas	28	2.1	33	4.0	61		
	Kerosene	32	2.4	36	4.4	68		
	Wood	5	0.4	1	0.1	6		
	Agricultural crop waste	2	0.2	0	0	2		
Instrument used for cooking	Dung cakes	14	1.1	14	1.7	28	62.828	0.001
	Stove	153	11.5	21	2.5	174		
	Chullah	194	14.6	100	12.1	294		
	Open fire	3	0.2	5	0.6	8		
	Gas	983	73.7	701	84.8	1684		

Ventilation in kitchen	Yes	1100	82.5	718	86.8	1818	7.079	0.008
	No	233	17.5	109	13.2	342		
Physical Activity	Vigorous intensity activity	138	10.4	46	5.6	184	15.028	0.001
	Moderate intensity activity	1195	89.6	781	94.4	1976		
No. of days physical activity is done	1 Day	23	1.7	4	0.5	27	49.362	0.001
	2 Days	46	3.5	6	0.7	52		
	3 Days	28	2.1	1	0.1	29		
	4 Days	36	2.7	9	1.1	45		
	5 Days	47	3.5	24	2.9	71		
	6 Days	29	2.2	13	1.6	42		
	7 Days	1124	84.3	770	93.1	1894		
Time do you spend doing physical activity on a particular day	1 Hour	338	25.4	165	20.0	503	22.327	0.014
	2 Hours	367	27.5	262	31.7	629		
	3 Hours	269	20.2	177	21.4	446		
	4 Hours	161	12.1	117	14.1	278		
	5 Hours	73	5.5	36	4.4	109		
	6 Hours	45	3.4	29	3.5	74		
	7 Hours	43	3.2	17	2.1	60		
	8 Hours	36	2.7	20	2.4	56		
	9 Hours	0	0	3	0.4	3		
	10 Hours	1	0.1	1	0.1	2		
Types of physical activity	Walking	269	20.2	66	8.0	335	71.333	0.001
	Running	19	1.4	5	0.6	24		
	Gym	11	0.8	3	0.4	14		
	Yoga	2	0.2	0	0	2		
	Agricultural work	2	0.2	1	0.1	3		
	Animal husbandry	0	0	2	0.2	2		
	Labour work /MGNREGA	10	0.8	7	0.8	17		
	Gardening	1	0.1	1	0.1	2		
	Household work	985	73.9	725	87.7	1710		
	Stitching or Tailoring	14	1.1	8	1.0	22		
	Any other	20	1.5	9	1.1	29		
No. of hours do you watch television in a day	0 Hour	546	41.0	299	36.2	845	9.414	0.152
	1 Hour	406	30.5	252	30.5	658		
	2 Hours	277	20.8	205	24.8	482		
	3 Hours	80	6.0	59	7.1	139		
	4 Hours	13	1.0	8	1.0	21		
	5 Hours	5	0.4	3	0.4	8		
	6 Hours	6	0.5	1	0.1	7		
No. of hours do you use mobile phone in a day	0 Hour	41	3.1	47	5.7	88	48.491	0.001
	1 Hour	578	43.4	371	44.9	949		
	2 Hours	440	33.0	296	35.8	736		
	3 Hours	138	10.4	88	10.6	226		
	4 Hours	54	4.1	15	1.8	69		
	5 Hours	51	3.8	9	1.1	60		
	6 Hours	31	2.3	1	0.1	32		
Sleeping hours	5 Hours	27	2.0	82	9.9	109	74.871	0.001
	6 Hours	241	18.1	178	21.5	419		

	7 Hours	524	39.3	276	33.4	800		
	8 Hours	466	35.0	252	30.5	718		
	9 Hours	59	4.4	30	3.6	89		
	10 Hours	16	1.2	9	1.1	25		
Stress	Yes	310	23.3	236	28.5	546	7.536	0.006
	No	1023	76.7	591	71.5	1614		
Emotional stress	No	1098	82.4	645	78.0	1743	6.279	0.014
	Yes	235	17.6	182	22.0	417		
Physical stress	No	1277	95.8	756	91.4	2033	17.727	0.001
	Yes	56	4.2	71	8.6	127		
Financial stress	No	1187	89.0	734	88.8	1921	0.044	0.833
	Yes	146	11.0	93	11.2	239		

In this study of 2160 individuals, several dietary factors showed significant associations with hypertension. Hypertensive participants had significantly different cereal servings ($P=0.005$), legume frequency ($P=0.001$), and leafy vegetable frequency ($P=0.001$), although not their respective serving sizes. Intake frequency of non-leafy vegetables ($P=0.001$), salad ($P=0.027$) and salad servings ($P=0.048$) also differed. Dairy product servings ($P=0.001$), non-vegetarian meal frequency ($P=0.002$) and tea servings ($P=0.025$) were significantly related to hypertension. Additional significant associations were found in consumption frequency and servings of fast food ($P=0.017$ and $P=0.001$, respectively), junk food ($P=0.007$ and $P=0.001$), dry fruits ($P=0.001$), fresh juice ($P=0.001$), caffeine-rich drinks ($P=0.001$ for both frequency and servings), and water intake ($P=0.001$). Hypertensive females also showed significant differences in type of oil/fat used ($P=0.003$), frequency of changing oil/fat ($P=0.020$), sugar intake ($P=0.003$), salt intake ($P=0.001$), table salt use ($P=0.041$), and pickle consumption ($P=0.001$) (Table 3).

TABLE III

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIETARY CHARACTERISTICS AND HYPERTENSION STATUS

		HYPERTENSION				Total (2160)	Chi-square value	P-value
		Normotensives		Hypertensives				
		No. of cases (n=1333)	% age	No. of cases (n=827)	% age			
Cereals	1 Day	3	0.2	3	0.4	6		
	2 Days	20	1.5	6	0.7	26		

	3 Days	9	0.7	2	0.2	11	5.131	0.274
	4 Days	5	0.4	2	0.2	7		
	7 Days	1296	97.2	814	98.4	2110		
Servings of cereals	1 serving	200	15.0	165	20.0	365	10.785	0.005
	2 servings	57	4.3	24	2.9	81		
	3 servings	1076	80.7	638	77.1	1714		
Legumes	0	4	0.3	1	0.1	5	24.789	0.001
	1 Day	135	10.1	43	5.2	178		
	2 Days	374	28.1	209	25.3	583		
	3 Days	259	19.4	187	22.6	446		
	4 Days	207	15.5	142	17.2	349		
	5 Days	185	13.9	121	14.6	306		
	6 Days	94	7.1	79	9.6	173		
Servings of legumes	0	4	0.3	1	0.1	5	1.36	0.715
	1 serving	803	60.2	506	61.2	1309		
	2 servings	450	33.8	268	32.4	718		
	3 servings	76	5.7	52	6.3	128		
Leafy vegetables	0	16	1.2	6	0.7	22	31.907	0.001
	1 Day	146	11.0	43	5.2	189		
	2 Days	301	22.6	164	19.8	465		
	3 Days	292	21.9	199	24.1	491		
	4 Days	219	16.4	146	17.7	365		
	5 Days	196	14.7	144	17.4	340		
	6 Days	96	7.2	85	10.3	181		
Servings of leafy vegetables	0	16	1.2	6	0.7	22	3.102	0.376
	1 serving	831	62.3	510	61.7	1341		
	2 servings	404	30.3	247	29.9	651		
	3 servings	82	6.2	64	7.7	146		
Non leafy vegetables	0	11	0.8	3	0.4	14		
	1 Day	122	9.2	28	3.4	150		

	2 Days	377	28.3	210	25.4	587	38.729	0.001
	3 Days	278	20.9	197	23.8	475		
	4 Days	209	15.7	129	15.6	338		
	5 Days	166	12.5	116	14.0	282		
	6 Days	104	7.8	93	11.2	197		
	7 Days	66	5.0	51	6.2	117		
Non leafy vegetables servings	0	11	0.8	3	0.4	14	1.996	0.369
	1 serving	829	62.2	507	61.3	1336		
	2 servings	493	37.0	317	38.3	810		
Salad	0	25	1.9	26	3.1	51	15.752	0.027
	1 Day	46	3.5	23	2.8	69		
	2 Days	51	3.8	24	2.9	75		
	3 Days	64	4.8	40	4.8	104		
	4 Days	55	4.1	43	5.2	98		
	5 Days	110	8.3	91	11.0	201		
	6 Days	86	6.5	69	8.3	155		
	7 Days	896	67.2	511	61.8	1407		
Salad servings	0	451	33.8	246	29.7	697	3.901	0.048
	1 serving	882	66.2	581	70.3	1463		
Fruits	0	21	1.6	13	1.6	34	3.512	0.622
	1 Day	793	59.5	525	63.5	1318		
	2 Days	191	14.3	106	12.8	297		
	3 Days	144	10.8	81	9.8	225		
	4 Days	74	5.6	41	5.0	115		
	5 Days	110	8.3	61	7.4	171		
Fruits servings	0	21	1.6	13	1.6	34	2.583	0.275
	1 serving	1125	84.4	677	81.9	1802		
	2 servings	187	14.0	137	16.6	324		
Dairy products	0	28	2.1	17	2.1	45		
	1 Day	14	1.1	10	1.2	24		
	2 Days	13	1.0	13	1.6	26		
	3 Days	21	1.6	14	1.7	35		

	4 Days	2	0.2	6	0.7	8	10.623	0.156
	5 Days	5	0.4	0	0	5		
	6 Days	2	0.2	0	0	2		
	7 Days	1248	93.6	767	92.7	2015		
Dairy products serving	0	28	2.1	17	2.1	45	17.887	0.001
	1 serving	396	29.7	269	32.5	665		
	2 servings	824	61.8	521	63.0	1345		
	3 servings	85	6.4	20	2.4	105		
Fish	0	1300	97.5	808	97.7	2108	3.44	0.632
	1 Day	6	0.5	7	0.8	13		
	2 Days	12	0.9	5	0.6	17		
	3 Days	7	0.5	5	0.6	12		
	4 Days	5	0.4	1	0.1	6		
	5 Days	3	0.2	1	0.1	4		
Fish servings	0	1299	97.4	809	97.8	2108	0.385	0.825
	1 serving	24	1.8	12	1.5	36		
	2 servings	10	0.8	6	0.7	16		
Non-vegetarian meals	0	1247	93.5	771	93.2	2018	20.811	0.002
	1 Day	6	0.5	16	1.9	22		
	2 Days	46	3.5	13	1.6	59		
	3 Days	25	1.9	17	2.1	42		
	4 Days	8	0.6	7	0.8	15		
	5 Days	1	0.1	2	0.2	3		
	6 Days	0	0	1	0.1	1		
Non-vegetarian meals servings	0	1247	93.5	771	93.2	2018	0.818	0.664
	1 serving	79	5.9	49	5.9	128		
	2 servings	7	0.5	7	0.8	14		
Eggs	0	1240	93.0	773	93.5	2013		
	1 Day	10	0.8	7	0.8	17		
	2 Days	35	2.6	17	2.1	52		
	3 Days	20	1.5	17	2.1	37		

	4 Days	13	1.0	7	0.8	20	4.759	0.689
	5 Days	5	0.4	4	0.5	9		
	6 Days	2	0.2	1	0.1	3		
	7 Days	8	0.6	1	0.1	9		
Eggs servings	0	1240	93.0	773	93.5	2013	0.427	0.808
	1 serving	82	6.2	46	5.6	128		
	2 servings	11	0.8	8	1.0	19		
Carbonated drinks	0	460	34.5	296	35.8	756	7.194	0.207
	1 Day	327	24.5	205	24.8	532		
	2 Days	251	18.8	137	16.6	388		
	3 Days	131	9.8	87	10.5	218		
	4 Days	107	8.0	80	9.7	187		
	5 Days	57	4.3	22	2.7	79		
Carbonated drinks servings	0	460	34.5	296	35.8	756	6.002	0.05
	1 serving	836	62.7	521	63.0	1357		
	2 servings	37	2.8	10	1.2	47		
Fresh juice	0	645	48.4	465	56.2	1110	19.417	0.001
	1 Day	242	18.2	151	18.3	393		
	2 Days	267	20.0	141	17.0	408		
	3 Days	179	13.4	70	8.5	249		
Fresh juice servings	0	645	48.4	465	56.2	1110	12.558	0.001
	1 serving	688	51.6	362	43.8	1050		
Caffeine rich drinks	0	382	28.7	277	33.5	659	90.71	0.001
	1 Day	291	21.8	197	23.8	488		
	2 Days	291	21.8	226	27.3	517		
	3 Days	108	8.1	80	9.7	188		
	4 Days	37	2.8	12	1.5	49		
	5 Days	22	1.7	11	1.3	33		
	6 Days	10	0.8	0	0	10		
	7 Days	192	14.4	24	2.9	216		
Caffeine rich drinks servings	0	382	28.7	277	33.5	659		
	1 serving	927	69.5	547	66.1	1474		

	2 servings	23	1.7	3	0.4	26	13.272	0.004
	3 servings	1	0.1	0	0	1		
Tea	0	17	1.3	4	0.5	21	10.482	0.163
	1 Day	7	0.5	1	0.1	8		
	2 Days	5	0.4	0	0	5		
	3 Days	3	0.2	2	0.2	5		
	4 Days	3	0.2	2	0.2	5		
	5 Days	11	0.8	7	0.8	18		
	6 Days	20	1.5	19	2.3	39		
	7 Days	1267	95.0	792	95.8	2059		
Tea servings	0	17	1.3	4	0.5	21	11.123	0.025
	1 serving	118	8.9	56	6.8	174		
	2 servings	989	74.2	612	74.0	1601		
	3 servings	195	14.6	150	18.1	345		
	4 servings	14	1.1	5	0.6	19		
Sweets	0	313	23.5	165	20.0	478	13.424	0.062
	1 Day	331	24.8	210	25.4	541		
	2 Days	328	24.6	184	22.2	512		
	3 Days	186	14.0	141	17.0	327		
	4 Days	87	6.5	70	8.5	157		
	5 Days	46	3.5	37	4.5	83		
	6 Days	6	0.5	1	0.1	7		
	7 Days	36	2.7	19	2.3	55		
Sweets Servings	0	313	23.5	165	20.0	478	7.503	0.057
	1 serving	960	72.0	637	77.0	1597		
	2 servings	54	4.1	22	2.7	76		
	3 servings	6	0.5	3	0.4	9		
Fast food	0	265	19.9	206	24.9	471	17.063	0.017
	1 Day	399	29.9	235	28.4	634		
	2 Days	228	17.1	111	13.4	339		
	3 Days	158	11.9	98	11.9	256		
	4 Days	129	9.7	76	9.2	205		

	5 Days	99	7.4	76	9.2	175		
	6 Days	31	2.3	19	2.3	50		
	7 Days	24	1.8	6	0.7	30		
Fast food servings	0	265	19.9	206	24.9	471	15.508	0.001
	1 serving	1009	75.7	605	73.2	1614		
	2 servings	56	4.2	15	1.8	71		
	3 servings	3	0.2	1	0.1	4		
Junk food	0	336	25.2	248	30.0	584	19.516	0.007
	1 Day	384	28.8	230	27.8	614		
	2 Days	203	15.2	120	14.5	323		
	3 Days	163	12.2	95	11.5	258		
	4 Days	93	7.0	66	8.0	159		
	5 Days	78	5.9	49	5.9	127		
	6 Days	32	2.4	10	1.2	42		
	7 Days	44	3.3	9	1.1	53		
Junk food servings	0	336	25.2	248	30.0	584	32.765	0.001
	1 serving	914	68.6	568	68.7	1482		
	2 servings	68	5.1	10	1.2	78		
	3 servings	11	0.8	1	0.1	12		
	4 servings	4	0.3	0	0	4		
Dry fruits	0	334	25.1	293	35.4	627	43.016	0.001
	1 Day	216	16.2	105	12.7	321		
	2 Days	88	6.6	30	3.6	118		
	3 Days	60	4.5	29	3.5	89		
	4 Days	23	1.7	3	0.4	26		
	5 Days	20	1.5	7	0.8	27		
	6 Days	4	0.3	1	0.1	5		
	7 Days	588	44.1	359	43.4	947		
Dry fruits servings	0	334	25.1	295	35.7	629	33.308	0.001
	1 serving	943	70.7	516	62.4	1459		
	2 servings	54	4.1	16	1.9	70		
	3 servings	2	0.2	0	0	2		

Water consumption	0	205	15.4	68	8.2	273	52.167	0.001
	1 Day	510	38.3	302	36.5	811		
	2 Days	413	31.0	270	32.6	683		
	3 Days	134	10.1	89	10.8	223		
	4 Days	48	3.6	61	7.4	109		
	5 Days	17	1.3	32	3.9	49		
	6 Days	6	0.5	5	0.6	11		
Type of oil/fat	1 litre	881	66.1	586	70.9	1467	17.789	0.003
	2 litres	25	1.9	10	1.2	35		
	3 litres	6	0.5	2	0.2	8		
	4 litres	606	45.5	447	54.1	1075		
	5 litres	1103	82.7	673	81.4	1776		
	6 litres	67	5.0	51	6.2	118		
Change oil or fat regularly	Yes	302	22.7	224	27.1	526	5.437	0.020
	No	1031	77.3	603	72.9	1634		
Average intake of sugar daily	Very mild	328	24.6	213	25.8	541	13.84	0.003
	Mild	893	67.0	578	69.9	1471		
	Moderate	105	7.9	32	3.9	137		
	Severe	7	0.5	4	0.5	11		
Average intake of salt daily	Very mild	323	24.2	178	21.5	501	17.548	0.001
	Mild	382	28.7	185	22.4	567		
	Moderate	495	37.1	369	44.6	864		
	Severe	133	10.0	95	11.5	228		
Table salt	Yes	443	33.2	311	37.6	754	4.94	0.041
	No	890	66.8	516	62.4	1406		
Pickles	Yes	726	54.5	338	40.9	1064	37.728	0.001
	No	607	45.5	489	59.1	1096		

IV. Discussion

Dietary habits showed high weekly consumption of staples like cereals and dairy, while fish and non-vegetarian meals were rarely consumed. Hypertensive individuals reported higher average sugar and salt intake, as well as a greater likelihood of adding table salt to meals and consuming pickles. Lifestyle factors also differed, with hypertensive individuals less active and more likely to use traditional cooking methods.

Only a limited number of studies have explored the long-term relationship between dietary variety and the risk of developing hypertension [20]-[22].

The various types of fats- saturated, omega-3 polyunsaturated, omega-6 polyunsaturated, monounsaturated and omega-3 fats have received the most attention for their potential benefits in lowering blood pressure. The Omni Heart trial demonstrated that partially replacing carbohydrates with dietary fat, specifically 21% of total energy intake from monounsaturated fats primarily sourced from olive and canola oils, led to a reduction in systolic blood pressure by 2.9 mmHg [23]. Supporting this, a meta-analysis of nine randomized controlled trials found that diets high in monounsaturated fats significantly reduced both systolic and diastolic blood pressure, with average reductions of 2.26 mmHg and 1.15 mmHg, respectively [24].

In our research, we found that individuals who regularly consumed a wider range of food groups had a significantly lower risk of experiencing new-onset hypertension. This finding supports the idea that no single food can supply all the essential nutrients the body requires. By including different types of foods in the diet, individuals are more likely to achieve balanced nutrient intake.

Furthermore, a diverse diet may support greater microbial diversity in the gut, potentially enhancing the intake and metabolism of various bioactive compounds important for maintaining overall health and preventing disease [25]-[27]. Several epidemiological studies have previously explored the association between food group intake levels and hypertension risk [28]. Supporting this body of evidence, Wei Y et al. (2025) also observed that higher consumption of legumes, fruits and eggs was linked to a reduced likelihood of developing new-onset hypertension [29]. In Present study a significant difference in how often legumes are consumed between individuals with and without hypertension ($\chi^2=24.789$). Hypertensive individuals consumed more servings of cereals per day ($P=0.005$), fewer leafy vegetables ($P=0.001$), and more non-leafy vegetables ($P=0.001$) compared to those without hypertension.

The mineral composition of legumes- especially their magnesium, calcium and potassium content was thought to play a role in decreasing peripheral vascular resistance. This physiological benefit was potentially linked to elevated levels of vasodilators such as prostacyclin and nitric oxide, and lowered concentrations of angiotensin II [30]-[31].

Regarding dietary habits, hypertensive individuals did not differ significantly from their non-hypertensive counterparts in their tendency to change cooking oils or fats regularly ($P=0.877$). However, they demonstrated higher average intakes of sugar ($P=0.006$) and salt ($P=0.007$), were more likely to add table salt during meals ($P=0.013$) and consumed pickles more frequently ($P=0.001$).

These findings highlight important associations between lifestyle and dietary practices and the prevalence of hypertension, suggesting that targeted interventions could effectively reduce cardiovascular risk factors in this population.

Sacks et al. (2001) study compared the effects of reduced dietary sodium and the DASH diet on blood pressure in individuals with hypertension. Results indicated that both interventions significantly lowered blood pressure, with the DASH diet showing superior results [32].

Mozaffarian et al. (2011) analyzed dietary changes and their impact on weight gain and hypertension in both men and women. It found that diets high in refined carbohydrates and sugars were linked to increased risk of hypertension over time [33].

V. Conclusion

This study highlights a strong association between dietary patterns and hypertension. Hypertensive individuals consumed more salt, sugar, pickles and calorie-dense foods while showing lower dietary diversity. In contrast, greater intake of legumes, fruits, leafy vegetables and monounsaturated fats was linked to a reduced risk of developing hypertension. Promoting dietary variety, reducing excessive sodium and sugar intake and encouraging healthier cooking practices may serve as effective strategies in hypertension prevention and management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors are thankful to Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University for providing facilities for carrying out research work. I also extend gratitude towards my co-authors for rendering me support to complete this research work.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

RK: Contributed to the study's conception and design, participated in data collection and was actively involved in manuscript writing. **CKS:** Contributed to study planning, participated in data acquisition and analysis and assisted in manuscript preparation and review. **MA:** Involved in study design and data interpretation, and contributed significantly to data analysis. **AC:** Participated in data analysis, interpretation and contributed to the preparation and revision of the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sekhon CK, Kaur R, Airi M. Incidence of hypertension and its risk factors: a systematic review. *Int J Community Med Public Health* 2024;11(3):1282-1290. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20240633>
- [2] Qin X, Zhang Y, Cai Y, He M, Sun L, Fu J, et al. Prevalence of obesity, abdominal obesity and associated factors in hypertensive adults aged 45-75 years. *Clin Nutr* 2013;32(3):361-367. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2012.08.005>
- [3] Zhang Y, Liu M, Zhou C, Zhang Z, He P, Li Q, et al. Inverse association between dietary vitamin A intake and new-onset hypertension. *Clin Nutr* 2021;40(5):2868-2875. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2021.04.004>
- [4] Wu Q, Zhou C, Ye Z, Liu M, Zhang Z, He P, et al. Relationship of several serum folate forms with the prevalence of hypertension. *Precis Nutr* 2023;2(4):1-8. DOI: 10.1097/PN9.0000000000000058
- [5] Onwuzo C, Olukorode JO, Omokore OA, Odunaike OS, Omiko R, Osaghae OW, et al. DASH diet: a review of its scientifically proven hypertension reduction and health benefits. *Cureus* 2023;15(9):1-6. DOI: 10.7759/cureus.44692
- [6] Guo F, Zhang Q, Yin Y, Liu Y, Jiang H, Yan N, et al. Legume consumption and risk of hypertension in a prospective cohort of Chinese men and women. *Br J Nutr* 2020;123(5):564-573. DOI:10.1017/S0007114519002812
- [7] Liu MW, Yu HJ, Yuan S, Song Y, Tang BW, Cao ZK, et al. Association between fruit and vegetable intake and the risk of hypertension among Chinese adults: a longitudinal study. *Eur J Nutr* 2018; 57:2639-2647. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-018-1687-0>
- [8] Wang Z, Huang Q, Wang L, Jiang H, Wang Y, Wang H, et al. Moderate intake of lean red meat was associated with lower risk of elevated blood pressure in Chinese women: results from the China Health and Nutrition Survey, 1991-2015. *Nutr* 2020;12(5):1-15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12051369>

- [9] Meyer A, Klotz J. Dietary factors and hypertension: A review. *Curr Hypertens Rep* 2019;21(5):39. DOI: 10.1007/s11906-019-0965-0.
- [10] Zhou B, Huxley R. The role of dietary factors in the development of hypertension. *J Hypertens* 2009;27(5):993-1001. DOI:10.1097/HJH.0b013e32832b9f72.
- [11] The WHO STEPwise Approach to Noncommunicable Disease Risk Factor Surveillance. World Health Organization; 2017. Available from: <https://www.who.int/ncds/surveillance/steps/> [Last Accessed 03 May, 2024].
- [12] Government of Punjab. Available from: <https://punjab.gov.in/state-profile/> [Last Accessed 03 May, 2024].
- [13] Wani RT. Socioeconomic status scales-modified Kuppaswamy and Udai Pareekh's scale updated for 2019. *J Family Med Prim Care* 2019;8(6):1846-1849. DOI: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_288_19
- [14] He L, Yan Y, Wang Y. Identifying excessive intake of oil and salt to prevent and control hypertension: a latent class analysis. *Front Cardiovasc Med* 2022;9:1-10. DOI: 10.3389/fcvm.2022.782639.
- [15] Rust P, Ekmekcioglu C. Impact of salt intake on the pathogenesis and treatment of hypertension. *Hypertension: from basic research to clinical practice. Adv Exp Med Biol* 2017;956:61-84. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/5584_2016_147
- [16] Tian X, Huang Y, Wang H. Deviation of Chinese adults' diet from the Chinese food pagoda 2016 and its association with adiposity. *Nutr* 2017;9(9):1-13. DOI: 10.3390/nu9090995.
- [17] Lim JU, Lee JH, Kim JS, Hwang YI, Kim TH, Lim SY, et al. Comparison of World Health Organization and Asia-Pacific body mass index classifications in COPD patients. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis* 2017;12:2465-2475. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2147/COPD.S141295>
- [18] ICMR (2010). Nutrient Requirements and Recommended Dietary Allowance for Indians. A Report of the Expert Group of the Indian Council of Medical Research, New Delhi.
- [19] Bell K, Twiggs J, Olin BR, Date IR. Hypertension: the silent killer: updated JNC-8 guideline recommendations. *Ala Pharm Assoc* 2015;334:4222.
- [20] Azadbakht L, Mirmiran P, Esmailzadeh A. Dietary diversity score and cardiovascular risk factors in Tehranian adults. *Public Health Nutr* 2006;9(6):728-736. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1079/PHN2005887>

- [21] Motamedi A, Ekramzadeh M, Bahramali E, Farjam M, Homayounfar R. Diet quality in relation to the risk of hypertension among Iranian adults: cross-sectional analysis of Fasa PERSIAN cohort study. *Nutr. J* 2021;20(1):1-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12937-021-00717-1>
- [22] Oliveira EP, Camargo KF, Castanho GK, Nicola M, Portero-McLellan KC, Burini RC. Dietary variety is a protective factor for elevated systolic blood pressure. *Arq Bras Cardiol* 2012;98(4):338-343. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0066-782X2012005000020>
- [23] Appel LJ, Sacks FM, Carey VJ, Obarzanek E, Swain JF, Miller ER, et al. Effects of protein, monounsaturated fat, and carbohydrate intake on blood pressure and serum lipids: results of the Omni Heart randomized trial. *JAMA* 2005;294(19):2455-2464. DOI: 10.1001/jama.294.19.2455
- [24] Schwingshackl L, Strasser B, Hoffmann G. Effects of monounsaturated fatty acids on cardiovascular risk factors: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Nutr Metab* 2011;59(2-4):176-186. DOI: 10.1159/000334071.
- [25] Claesson MJ, Jeffery IB, Conde S, Power SE, O'connor EM, Cusack S, et al. Gut microbiota composition correlates with diet and health in the elderly. *Nature* 2012;488(7410):178-184. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11319>
- [26] Sakandar HA, Zhang H. Precision probiotics: does one-size-fit-all? *Precis Nutr* 2022;1(2):1-3. DOI: 10.1097/PN9.000000000000015
- [27] Bernstein MA, Tucker KL, Ryan ND, O'NEILL EF, Clements KM, Nelson ME, et al. Higher dietary variety is associated with better nutritional status in frail elderly people. *J Am Diet Assoc* 2002;102(8):1096-1104. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223\(02\)90246-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223(02)90246-4)
- [28] Kim J, Kim J. Association between fruit and vegetable consumption and risk of hypertension in middle-aged and older Korean adults. *J Acad Nutr Diet* 2018;118(8): 1438-1449. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jand.2017.08.122>
- [29] Wei Y, Su X, Wang G, Zu C, Meng Q, Zhang Y, et al. Quantity and variety of food groups consumption and the risk of hypertension in adults: a prospective cohort study. *Hypertens Res* 2025;48(3):971-982. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41440-024-02036-4>
- [30] Stolarz-Skrzypek K, Bednarski A, Czarnecka D, Kawecka-Jaszcz K, Staessen JA. Sodium and potassium and the pathogenesis of hypertension. *Curr Hypertens Rep* 2013;15:122-130. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-013-0331-x>
- [31] Schutten JC, Joosten MM, de Borst MH, Bakker SJ. Magnesium and blood pressure: a physiology-based approach. *Adv Chronic Kidney Dis* 2018;25(3):244-250. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ackd.2017.12.003>

[32] Sacks FM, Svetkey LP, Vollmer WM, Appel LJ, Bray GA, Harsha D, et al. Effects on blood pressure of reduced dietary sodium and the Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH) diet. *N Engl J Med* 2001;344(1):3-10. DOI: 10.1056/NEJM200101043440101

[33] Mozaffarian D, Hao T, Rimm EB, Willett WC, Hu FB. Changes in diet and lifestyle and long-term weight gain in women and men. *N Engl J Med* 2011;364(25):2392-2404. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1014296